

FINANCIAL DEVELOPMENT, GOVERNANCE AND INCOME INEQUALITY: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS BETWEEN OECD COUNTRIES AND DEVELOPING COUNTRIES

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Abstract

This study re-examines the role of financial development in reducing income inequality by using a broader measure of financial development and a comparable Gini coefficient to represent income inequality. In addition, the direct effects of six dimensions of governance and the interactive effects of five dimensions of it with the left one namely corruption control on income inequality have been examined. The study utilizes a sample of 81 countries over a period of 17 years and applied a two-step system GMM method. The study confirms the U-shaped hypothesis of finance-income inequality nexus in the whole sample as well as in subsamples of Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) countries and developing countries. Among the six dimensions of governance, Corruption Control reduces income inequality directly only in developing countries and Government Effectiveness remains insignificant across all country groups. Regulatory Quality can reduce income inequality while combined with Corruption Control. This result is true in the whole sample and subsample of developing countries but not in OECD countries. The interactive effect of Rule of Law with Corruption Control contributes in reducing income inequality in general but this becomes insignificant in subsample analysis. Political Stability directly improves income distribution in general and when combined with Corruption Control it reduces income inequality in developing countries. In developing countries, its direct effect is found to be worsening income inequality which could be mitigated when it interacted with Corruption Control. Finally, only the interactive effect of Voice and Accountability with Corruption Control reduces income inequality in general but not in any subsample. Hence, government policies designed to handle intense income inequality would be effective under strong Corruption Control. Therefore, study suggests simultaneous improvement of corruption control and some specific government policies.

Keywords : *Financial Development, Governance, Income Inequality, Panel Data, System GMM Method.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Income inequality is increasing on an average throughout the whole world. This is not only a phenomenon of developing or least developed countries. Developed countries are also experiencing high income inequality. Developing countries experienced rising

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income inequality during the 1980s to 1990s (Alvaredo & Gasparini, 2015) which tend to decline slow enough to stay almost flat since 2000s (Ravallion, 2014). Besides, OECD countries are also experiencing sharply increased income inequality (Braconier et al., 2014) over the last three decades. As well as since 1990s, income inequality is increasing in transitional economies (Ivaschenko, 2001). The alarming issue is that officially stated statistics about income inequality often tend to underestimate the actual scenario (Xie & Zhou, 2014). Therefore, reducing income inequality has become essential and it is the 10th goal among 17 sustainable development goals (SDGs) adopted at the United Nations Sustainable Development Summit held in 2015 (UN DESA, 2019). Several targets have been set to achieve the goal including ensuring of social, political, and economic inclusion of all people; adopting non-discriminatory laws, policies and practices; implementing fiscal policies; ensuring the presence of representative and voice from developing countries in the international platform; regulating world financial markets and monitoring it. The effectiveness of these policies needs to be examined. Although finance plays an important role in reducing poverty, how it effects income inequality still remains paradoxical in alternative studies. Theoretical evidence (Galor & Zeira, 1993; Banerjee & Newman, 1993; Greenwood & Jovanovich, 1990; Korinek & Kreamer, 2014 and others) and empirical studies (Li et al., 1998; Jalilian & Kirkpatrick, 2002; Kappel, 2010 and others) reveal ambiguous findings such as either positive or negative and non-linear U-shaped or inverted U-shaped nexus of finance and income inequality. Lots of controversies have been found regarding the measurement of income inequality as Gini coefficients might not be comparable over time across countries. That's why this study uses Solt's (2016) Gini Coefficient collected from the Standardized World Income Inequality Database (SWIID) which is comparable across countries and time. Alternative measures of financial development have been adopted in previous studies such as bank credit, domestic credit to the private sector, liquid liabilities, or a composite index by mixing two or three indicators. But the overall multidimensional characteristics of financial development such as its depth, access and efficiency should be considered altogether. To represent good governance, corruption is extensively used in literature disregarding other dimensions of governance.

Therefore, the study attempts to contribute towards the relevant literature by (i) Re-examining the effects of finance on income inequality adopting the overall financial development index (a broader measure of financial development) and comparable Gini coefficients developed by International Monetary Fund (IMF), 2016 and Solt (2016) respectively; (ii) The study attempts to find out the individual effects of six components of worldwide governance indicators on income inequality. As well as the effects of corruption controls interacting with the rest of the indicators have also been examined and (iii) Finally, the study examines whether the effects of financial development and governance indicators on income inequality are different in subsamples of OECD countries and developing countries or not.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section-2 reviews theoretical and empirical literature; Section-3 deals with the methodology. Following these, empirical findings will be analyzed in section-4. Finally, section-5 represents the conclusion.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Financial Development and Income inequality

2.1.1 Theoretical Background

The theoretical predictions about the impact of financial development on income distribution are found to be ambiguous (Demirguc & Levine, 2009). Galor and Zeira (1993) argued that financial development reduces income inequality through improved capital allocation and increased credit availability which increases the investment in human capital and collateral use by mass people. Similarly, Banerjee and Newman (1993) predicted that as household's occupational choices depend on credit availability, better access to credit enable poor households to invest more in productive projects which narrows down the income distribution gap. Also, the finance-income inequality nexus might be inverse U-shaped. Income inequality might increase with improved financial conditions when economic development is lower by increasing financial access for people who already have those opportunities and after a mature phase, further financial development could reduce income inequality by creating benefits for a broader range of people (Greenwood & Jovanovic, 1990). In contrast, Korinek and Kreamer (2014) stated that when financial sector becomes more sophisticated, income inequality could be worsened with further development supporting a U-shaped effect of finance on income inequality. The justification is that with different compensation schemes, financial innovations, concentrated banking, etc. could increase the benefits for the top income group only and reduces for the rest of the people by encouraging risk-taking behavior and expectations. Also, the causality relationship between finance and income inequality might occur in both ways which will not be examined here as the study focuses on the impact of financial development on income inequality.

2.1.2 Empirical Evidence

Empirical studies have found paradoxical results like theoretical predictions. Several studies confirm that financial development reduces income inequality. For example, Li et al. (1998) find that financial development reduces income inequality as well as Jalilian and Kirkpatrick (2002) stated that it makes a clear contribution to poverty reduction. The former study was conducted for 40 developed and developing countries from 1947–1994. Using a larger sample (83 countries) over the period of 1960 to 1995, Clarke et al. (2006) also found that financial development leads to less income inequality in the long run. But the authors could not find any evidence of inverted U-shaped relationships. Again, Beck et al. (2007) showed that the income of the poorest quintile disproportionately increases with increases in private credit to GDP while the later reduces income inequality. Although financial development reduces both poverty and income inequality, the effect on later is less significant than the former (Kappel, 2010).

In contrast, income inequality could be worsened due to financial development (Rodriguez-Pose & Tselios, 2009; Gimet & Lagoarde-Segot, 2011). The former study

focused on European Union over the period 1995–2000 and the later one analyzed 49 developed and developing countries from 1994–2002. Jauch and Watzka (2015) also used a set of both developing and developed countries and found that financial development increases income inequality. In the case of highly developed countries, income inequality widening effects are found to be more obvious. Analyzing for 16 OECD countries, Roine et al. (2009) found that financial development significantly increases the relative income of rich people. Similarly, Denk and Cournède (2015) found that financial expansion has widened the income distribution gap in OECD countries. Several factors might work behind these findings. For example, in USA bank regulation increases monopolies of local banks by restricting competitions which increases income inequality (Beck et al., 2010) and rent-seeking behavior of firms, inefficient regulations, as well as rapid financial liberalization without strong political and economic institutions, causes further increase in income inequality (Stiglitz, 2013). The mechanisms could be different in developing countries. In developing countries, poor people do not get direct benefits from stock market development (Charlton, 2008). In Malaysia, bank and stock market development are not found to be significantly related to income inequality (Law & Tan, 2009). The historical existence of income inequality could also reinforce further income inequality through distortions, unequal access to finance and opportunities (Claessens & Perotti, 2007).

There is also evidence about the existence of the threshold level of development below which financial development increases (or decreases) income inequality and after which financial development decreases (or increases) income inequality. Kim and Lin (2011) emphasized that after a minimum level of financial development income gap will be narrowed. That means financial development contributes to reducing income inequality up to a point (Tan & Law, 2012; Park & Shin, 2015, and others). After that point, further financial development contributes to greater income inequality. Previous studies also tried to find other factors that could help to get lower income inequality with financial development. Prete (2013) studied the relevance of financial literacy and found that countries having higher economic literacy faces less growth in income inequality. Law et al. (2014) and Delis et al. (2014) identified the necessities of a certain level of institutional quality to get the beneficial impact of enhanced financial markets. Likewise, Rajan and Zingales (2003) argue that controlling weak political institutions allow rich people to get more from financial development than the poor. Higher educational enrolment along with financial development can make more equal distribution of income for African countries (Batuo et al., 2010). While maximum studies used either bank or stock market development, Seven and Coskun (2016) developed a composite indicator by adding aggregate bank development measures and aggregate stock market measures. The study found that income inequality increases with financial development.

2.2 Governance and Income Inequality

The theoretical background as well as empirical investigation about the effects of governance on income inequality started almost simultaneously. The study on this issue is relatively few and most of them either used only one or two indicators of

governance mostly corruption or constructed overall index for governance by aggregating them. The majority of these studies emphasized on good governance. For example, Gupta et al. (2001) predicted 11 points of increases in income inequality measured by the Gini coefficient due to increases in corruption by one standard deviation. Similarly, Tan and Law (2011) have adopted a corruption index from the International Country Risk Guide (ICRG) while examining the finance-income inequality relationship. The study found that an increased level of corruption significantly distorts income distribution. Applying non-parametric approach Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA), Nadia and Teheni (2014) constructed an overall governance index by using six dimensions of Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI) developed by Kaufmann et al. (2010). The study found that good governance reduces income inequality and positively associated with financial development at a high level of significance. But the authors found that financial development reduces income inequality only from 1998 to 2000. Also, implementation and establishment of policies to improve governance systems might be challenging by the presence of large-scale corruption (Epstein & Gang, 2017). Hence, the effectiveness of each component of governance indicators on income inequality might be different when they interact with corruption.

The contribution of the study in the literature is threefold. It attempts to re-examine the effects of finance on income inequality by using broader measure financial development and a comparable Gini coefficient for income inequality. After that, the effects of six dimensions of WGI on income inequality have been identified separately. In addition, whether the five dimensions effects vary while interacting with other dimensions namely Corruption Control have also been examined. Finally, by dividing the whole sample into two broad subsamples namely OECD countries and developing countries, this study analyses the differential effects of financial development and governance indicators in a different group of countries.

3. DATA, VARIABLE MEASUREMENT AND METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

3.1 Econometric Models and Research Hypothesis

A linear dynamic panel data model is first set up to test the alternative linear hypotheses of income inequality widening and income inequality narrowing. The model can be represented in its log-log form as follows:

$$gini_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 gini_{it-1} + \beta_2 FD_{it-1} + \beta_4 inflation_{it} + \beta_5 rgdp_{it} + u_{it} \dots\dots\dots 1(a)$$

Where subscript i stands for the number of countries and $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 81$. Also, subscript t stands for the number of years, $t = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 17$. The dependent variable, gini is the indicator of income inequality and lagged gini appeared as one of the explanatory variables. FD stands for financial development index. Other control variables inflation and real GDP are represented by inflation and rgdp. All of the variables are expressed in their logarithmic form except FD (financial development index) itself. The error term, $u_{it} = u_i + v_{it}$. Where, $u_i \sim iid(0, \delta_u^2)$ and $v_{it} \sim iid(0, \delta_v^2)$. They are independent of each other and among themselves. To avoid probable

endogeneity problem lagged financial development (FD_{it-1}) is included in this study by following Tan and Law’s (2012) study. Moreover, the effects of financial development might take time to reduce income inequality. Inflation is measured by the consumer price index and has been taken in a logarithmic term. Finally, RGDP indicates real gross domestic product. If $\beta_2 > 0$ and significant, financial development will widen income inequality. If $\beta_2 < 0$ and significant, financial development will reduce income inequality. The coefficient of inflation is expected to be positive since according to Ravallion and Datt (1999) inflation increases poverty and income inequality (Easterly & Fischer, 2001). The β_5 might be greater than zero or less than zero. If increased national income favors the poor more than the rich, it will impact positively and vice-versa.

The financial development and income inequality nexus might be different at a different level of financial development. These non-linear effects (the inverted U-shaped hypothesis) of financial development on income inequality as predicted by Greenwood and Jovanovic (1990), could be tested by including square term of financial development in equation 1(a) as follows:

$$gini_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 gini_{it-1} + \beta_2 FD_{it-1} + \beta_3 FD_{it-1}^2 + \beta_4 inflation_{it} + \beta_5 rgdp_{it} + u_{it} \dots 1(b)$$

The inverted hypotheses will be supported if $\beta_2 > 0$ and $\beta_3 < 0$. This means that when countries are at low stage of financial development (represented by FD_{it-1}), increases in financial development will increase income inequality (represented by $\beta_2 > 0$). But when countries reach at high level of financial development (represented by FD_{it-1}^2), further improvement of it will reduce income inequality (represented by $\beta_3 < 0$). By contrast, the existence of U-shaped hypothesis could be detected if $\beta_2 < 0$ and $\beta_3 > 0$. This means that when countries are at low stage of financial development (represented by FD_{it-1}), increases in financial development will decrease income inequality (represented by $\beta_2 < 0$). But when countries reach at high level of financial development (represented by FD_{it-1}^2), further improvement of it will increase income inequality (represented by $\beta_3 > 0$).

For the robustness test, using the private credit as a measurement of financial development instead of overall financial development index, equation 1(a) and 1(b) could be re-written as follows:

$$gini_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 gini_{it-1} + \beta_2 Private\ Credit_{it-1} + \beta_4 inflation_{it} + \beta_5 rgdp_{it} + u_{it} \dots 2(a)$$

$$gini_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 gini_{it-1} + \beta_2 Private\ Credit_{it-1} + \beta_3 Private\ Credit_{it-1}^2 + \beta_4 inflation_{it} + \beta_5 rgdp_{it} + u_{it} \dots 2(b)$$

The expected sign of private credit and other control variables are the same as they were made for equation 1(a) and 1(b). All of the variables except private credit are taken in their logarithmic form.

Since, Langbein and Knack (2010) stated that the six governance indicators represent the same broad concept of governance instead of different dimensions of good governance which has been further defended by Kaufmann et al. (2010). Therefore, including these

six dimensions in a single equation would exaggerate the collinearity problem. To avoid the problem, this study includes each of the governance indicators in separate equations. Regression equation 1(b) would be further extended by incorporating worldwide governance indicators to detect (i) the effects of each of the indicators separately (ii) as well as the effects of interacting each indicator with Corruption Control to identify whether their effect vary when they are combined with corruption control. At first, including log of Corruption Control, equation 1(b) could be extended as follows:

$$gini_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 gini_{it-1} + \beta_2 FD_{it-1} + \beta_3 FD_{it-1}^2 + \beta_4 inflation_{it} + \beta_5 rgdp_{it} + \beta_7 corruptioncont_{it} + u_{it} \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

The coefficient of corruption control, β_7 is expected to be negative. Since higher Corruption Control could make income distribution fair which narrows down the income inequality. The other five dimensions of governance indicators are represented by $governance_{it}$ in equation 4 (a) and 4(b).

$$gini_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 gini_{it-1} + \beta_2 FD_{it-1} + \beta_3 FD_{it-1}^2 + \beta_4 inflation_{it} + \beta_5 rgdp_{it} + \beta_7 governance_{it} + u_{it} \dots \dots \dots 4(a)$$

$$gini_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 gini_{it-1} + \beta_2 FD_{it-1} + \beta_3 FD_{it-1}^2 + \beta_4 inflation_{it} + \beta_5 rgdp_{it} + \beta_7 governance_{it} + \beta_8 (governance_{it} \times corruptioncont_{it}) + u_{it} \dots \dots \dots 4(b)$$

All of the governance indicators are expressed in their logarithmic term. Since five other dimensions of governance indicators except corruption are yet to include, equation 4(a) and 4 (b) will be estimated five times, each time using one of those five dimensions namely (i) Government Effectiveness; (ii) Regulatory Quality; (iii) Rule of Law; (iv) Political Stability and Absence of Violence: and (v) voice and Accountability to represent $Governance_{it}$. For example, in case of detecting the effects of Government Effectiveness, this indicator will be used in equation 4(a) and 4(b) to represent the variable $governance_{it}$.

In the case of Government Effectiveness, one could expect that $\beta_7 < 0$ in equation 4(a) and both $\beta_7 < 0$; $\beta_8 < 0$ in equation 4(b). As an increased level of Government Effectiveness increase the ability to reduce income inequality and this ability should be higher with a greater level of corruption control. While Regulatory Quality has been used, it could be expected that $\beta_7 < 0$ in equation 4(a) and both $\beta_7 < 0$; $\beta_8 < 0$ in equation 4(b). Since the increased level of Regulatory Quality should be associated with more uniform income distribution which should be even higher with a greater level of corruption control. Similarly, in equation 4(a) and 4(b), it could be expected that $\beta_7 < 0$ and both $\beta_7 < 0$; $\beta_8 < 0$ respectively. Enforcement of Rule of Law might improve the income inequality situation which should be even higher with a greater level of corruption control. While examining the effects of Political Stability and Absence of violence which indicate the state of Political Instability, the expected sign of β_7 in equation 4(a) and in equation 4(b) is greater than zero but expected sign of β_8 in equation 4(b) is negative. This could be well explained as increasing Political Instability might worsen the income inequality which should be mitigated with greater corruption control. Finally, an attempt will be made to

identify the effects of voice and accountability and its interaction with corruption control. Voice and Accountability indicate a country's citizens can participate in selecting their government, as well as freedom of expression, freedom of association, and free media. A greater ranking of this variable should be improving income inequality and this effect should be higher in a state of better corruption control. Therefore, it is expected that $\beta_7 < 0$ in equation 4(a) and both $\beta_7 < 0$; $\beta_8 > 0$ in equation 4(b).

Each of the equations will be further estimated for the whole sample, the subsample of OECD countries and subsample of developing countries. Since the number of transitional countries is not adequate to apply the system GMM method, that country group has not been used as a separate subsample. The details on the whole sample and subsamples are discussed in the following section.

3.2 Sample Selection

The sample size consists of total 81 countries where 35 are OECD countries, 37 are developing countries and the rest of them (9) are transitional (see details in Appendix, Table-A1). In order to maintain homogeneity among countries, they are chosen from High-income, Upper-middle income and Lower-middle income groups. The Low-income country group is excluded. All OECD countries belong to High-income group except Mexico which is an Upper-middle income country. The developing and transitional countries are chosen from Upper-middle income and Lower-middle income groups. The study period is chosen from 1998 to 2014. While choosing the study period, analyzing the most recent scenarios and minimizing the problem of missing data are given the highest priority since there are substantial missing values of the Gini Index.

3.3 Variable Descriptions

3.3.1 Financial Development Measurement

The financial-income inequality-growth literature has approximated financial development either by using bank development indicators or stock market development indicators or by using both. Since income inequality is influenced by the banking sector more than it is influenced by the stock market, researchers mostly use bank credit to represent financial development (Gimet & Lagoarde-Segot, 2011) and its data is available across countries over a long period of time (Demirgüç-Kunt & Levine, 2008). Private credit, liquid liabilities, domestic credit to GDP, etc. and stock market value traded, stock market turnover to GDP, etc. have been used by several studies (Acemoglu & Johnson, 2005; Clarke et al., 2006; Beck et al., 2007; Baltagi et al., 2007; Herger et al., 2007). Denoting the fact that financial development is a broader issue Kappel (2010) constructed a composite index (finance) by adding the private credit and market capitalization together. Also, Seven and Coskun (2016) developed three aggregate measures namely market aggregate, bank aggregate, and overall finance aggregate while the last one added the first two.

But over time with the increased complexity of financial sectors, bank-based financial systems could work better at one end, but on the other end, market-based financial systems could be more effective (Kpodar & Singh, 2011). Therefore, financial development should be explained using much broader concepts. Such an

overall index is developed by the International Monetary Fund (IMF). Nine indices are constructed to explain the financial development in terms of access, depth and efficiency (Svirydzenka, 2016) by IMF. Following a standard three steps process from the OECD Handbook on Constructing Composite Index (OECD, 2008), the overall Financial Development Index (FD) is constructed by aggregating the immediate lower two sub-indices namely Institutions and Market indices while each of these is constructed by adding three lower-level sub-indices of institutional access, depth and efficiency, and market access (see details in Appendix, Table-A2). The higher FD indicates that a country's financial system is extended beyond its structural and regulatory capabilities. Besides, this overall index, this study will also adopt one conventional measurement namely private credit to GDP (private credit) for comparison purposes collected from World Bank's Global Financial Development Database.

3.3.2 Income Inequality Measurement

Income inequality is reflected by the discriminative share of income held by the percentage of population of different income groups. If the lowest-ranked portions receive the smallest share of income and the highest-ranked portion receives the largest share of income, then income inequality is greater and vice versa. Mostly, the Gini coefficient or its growth has been used to capture income inequality. But the Gini coefficient has its limitation in making comparisons across countries and over time due to differences in geography, age, employment, the definition of welfare, the population covered, measurement scale, etc. Gini Index data are mostly collected from WIDER-WIID (World Institute for Development Economics Research) and the University of Texas Income inequality Projects (UTIP) databases. WIDER-WIID is less comparable as it collected data from several sources. Although UTIP data are more comparable, it is based on manufacturing wage inequalities while a very small portion of the population in some developing or transitional economies might be working in manufacturing sectors.

Thus, this study collects data on Gini coefficient from the Standardized World Income Inequality Database (SWIID) developed in 2016 (Version 6.2) by Solt (2016). SWIID standardizes the WIID database using various techniques to increase the comparability of the cross-national Gini index across time (Solt, 2009, 2016). The disposable (post-tax, post-transfer) Gini Index is taken which has also been used by Tan and Law (2012) etc.

3.3.3 Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI)

The worldwide governance indicators are chosen for the study. The WGI are produced by Daniel Kaufmann (Natural Resource Governance Institute and Brookings Institution) and Aart Kraay (World Bank Development Research Group) in 1999 and then adjusted further overtime. The WGI are composite governance indicators with six dimensions of governance (for details see Appendix, Table-A3). These six components are (i) Corruption Control; (ii) Government Effectiveness; (iii) Regulatory Quality; (iv) Rule of Law; (v) Political Stability & Absence of Violence;

and (vi) Voice & Accountability. The six composite WGI measures are useful as a tool for broad cross-country comparisons and for evaluating broad trends over time. However, they are often too blunt a tool to be useful in formulating specific governance reforms in country contexts. Such reforms, and evaluation of their progress, need to be informed by much more detailed and country-specific diagnostic data that can identify the relevant constraints on governance country circumstances.

3.3.4 Other Control Variables

Following finance-income inequality literature, Real GDP (GDP constant 2010 US\$) and Inflation measured by Consumer Price Index (CPI) are taken as control variables. Data for all these variables are collected from World Development Indicators (see Appendix, Table-A3 for details of all variables and data sources). Simon Kuznets and Nicholas Kaldor argued that there is a trade-off between growth and income inequality (Forbes, 2000) which got further empirical support by de Janvry and Sadoulet (2000). Moreover, inflation increases poverty and income inequality (Easterly & Fischer, 2001; Ravallion & Datt, 1999).

3.4 Methodology of the Study

The general dynamic panel model including p lags could be written as follows:

$$Gini_{it} = \sum_{j=1}^p \alpha_j Gini_{it-j} + \beta_i X_{it} + \gamma_i Z_{it} + v_i + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

Where X_{it} and Z_{it} represent the vector of exogenous and endogenous variables respectively. The country-specific effects are shown by v_i which is unobserved and ε_{it} represents idiosyncratic errors. Here, v_i and ε_{it} are assumed to be independent of i and t . Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method to estimate equation (5) would create “dynamic panel bias” due to possible collinearity among lagged dependent variables with v_i (Nickell, 1981) which could not be mitigated by fixed effect or random effect model (Nickell, 1981; Bond, 2002). The endogeneity problem might become severe if lagged dependent variables are correlated with explanatory variables (Baum, 2006). Increasing sample size would not be a solution to the problem. Such endogeneity problems are dealt with by two types of Generalized Methods of Moments (GMM) methods such as difference GMM (Arellano & Bond, 1991) or by system GMM (Blundell & Bond, 1998). Besides other conditions, to apply GMM methods, the number of panel units (N) should be greater than the number of the time period (T) and the lagged dependent variable should be exogenous (Roodman, 2009). Since the current study is conducted for 81 (N) countries over a period of 17 (T) years, it would be better to use GMM methods. Under the persistence level of the high autoregressive process, the system GMM is more efficient than the first difference GMM. Also, the system GMM utilizes two-moment conditions. Lagged levels and lagged differences are instrumented for both level and difference equations in this method to find appropriate instruments (Canavire-Bacarreza et al., 2013). According to Hwang and Sun (2015), two-step GMM estimators are considered as more efficient than one-step since the former has smaller asymptotic variance than the later. The authors also warned about using two-step GMM randomly.

This study chooses to apply a two-step system GMM with caution. The efficiency and validity of the estimated estimators depend on satisfying several assumptions. The idiosyncratic errors should not be autocorrelated but having the first-order autocorrelation is normal as first difference equations are taken but there should not be any second or higher-order autocorrelation. The existence of no second or higher-order autocorrelation is examined by Arellano and Bond's (1991) first-order (AR-1) and second-order (AR-2) autocorrelation tests. Also, the restriction of the overidentification test should be observed by Hansen and Sargan test while the former performs better than the later (Roodman, 2009). As well as the use of too many instruments could reduce the efficiency of estimator. Mileva (2007) stated that instruments should be lower than the number of groups. To reduce the number of instruments, the study chooses to combine them by using a collapse option as suggested by Roodman (2009). As well as only recent lagged values will be allowed since Arellano and Bover (1995) found that the recent lagged differences should be used as an instrument for the level equation to reduce the unnecessary moment conditions.

4. ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

4.1 Descriptive Analysis

Table-1 summarizes the basic information of financial development indicators, income inequality, WGI and four control variables both in level form and in corresponding logarithmic forms. And the correlation between Gini Index and all variables are shown in Table-2.

Table 1: Summary Statistics

Variable	Observations	Mean	Std. dev	Minimum	Maximum
Gini	1,375	36.99	8.63	22.5	60
FD	1,375	0.43	0.26	0.05	1
Private Credit	1,375	63.90	47.20	2.79	262.46
RGDP	1,375	6.90e+11	1.81e+12	3.94e+09	1.62e+13
Inflation	1,364	25.70	12.66	-30.86	293.68
Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI)					
Corruption Control	1,213	56.88	28.98	1.46	100
Govt. Effectiveness	1,213	61.48	26.19	7.18	100
Regulatory Quality	1,213	62.06	26.05	2.84	100
Rule of Law	1,213	57.59	28.99	0.47	100
Political Stability & AV	1,213	50.39	0.04	0.47	100
Voice and Accountancy	1,213	58.98	28.30	3.37	100

Note: All variables are shown in their level form. Some missing values of some governance indicators are extrapolated at a minimum level.

There are considerable variations in all variables across time and countries as seen in Table-1. For example, the lowest value of Gini index is 22.5 which prevails in Denmark, Belarus and Sweden for a couple of years and the highest value of Gini Index (60) is found in South Africa during 1998, 1999 and remains around 59 throughout the whole study period. The lowest value of the financial index (0) is found in Belarus, Armenia and other lower-income countries and the highest value (0.95) prevails in Australia. Denmark is found to be the highest position regarding all governance indicators except Political Stability which is found to be best in Finland and worst in Pakistan. The lowest value of Corruption Control, Government Effectiveness, and Voice & Accountability is found in Bangladesh, Côte d'Ivoire and Belarus respectively. Venezuela stands in the poorest position in terms of both Regulatory Quality and Rule of Law.

In Table-2, Gini coefficient is found to be negatively related to financial development, private credit as well as to their squared terms. Also, income inequality is negatively correlated with real GDP but positively related to inflation. Gini Index is found to have a negative correlation with all the governance indicators except with the Political Stability and Voice & Accountability. The last two indicators are positively related to income inequality.

Table 2 : Correlation between Gini Coefficient and other Variables

Variables	Gini
Gini	1.00
FD	- 0.48
FD Square	-0.46
Private Credit	-0.33
Private Credit Square	-0.28
RGDP	-0.07
Inflation	0.08
Corruption control	0.002
Govt. Effectiveness	-0.021
Regulatory Quality	-0.024
Rule of Law	-0.017
Political Stability & AV	0.016
Voice and Accountancy	0.023

Note: All of the variables are expressed in their level form.

4.2 Analysis of Regression Results

4.2.1 Financial Development and Income Inequality: Linear or Non-Linear Relationship?

The estimated results of Model-1(a) showing the linear relationship and Model-1 (b) showing non-linear relationship are represented in Table-3.

Table 3 : Income Inequality and Financial Development

(1) Variable	Model-1(a) : Linear Effects of FD			Model-1(b) : Non-Linear Effects of FD		
	(2) Whole Sample	(3) OECD Countries	(4) Developing Countries	(5) Whole Sample	(6) OECD Countries	(7) Developing Countries
L1. Gini	0.89 (0.00) ***	0.66 (0.00) ***	0.92 (0.00) ***	0.87 (0.00) ***	0.08 (0.00) ***	0.91 (0.00) ***
L1. FD	-0.06 (0.08) *	-0.05 (0.23)	-0.13 (0.05) *	-0.42 (0.00) ***	-0.61 (0.02) **	-0.59 (0.01) **
L1. FD ²				0.31 (0.00) ***	0.42 (0.02) **	0.49 (0.04) **
inflation	0.02 (0.10)	0.01 (0.78)	0.02 (0.19)	-0.002 (0.67)	-0.02 (0.51)	0.005 (0.61)
rgdp	0.01 (0.07) *	0.03 (0.07) *	0.01 (0.01) **	0.02 (0.00) **	0.02 (0.03) **	0.02 (0.05) *
Constant	0.10 (0.70)	0.47 (0.48)	-0.08 (0.90)	0.13 (0.64)	0.021 (0.75)	-0.01 (0.83)
Observations no.	1284	559	581	1284	559	581
Group no.	81	35	37	81	35	37
Instruments no.	21	21	21	21	21	21
Diagnostic Test Results						
F-Value	57.46	9.59	17.21	60.09	6.27	22.98
Prob> F	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
AR (1) P-value	0.02	0.42	0.07	0.01	0.06	0.21
AR (2) P-value	0.02	0.26	0.04	0.03	0.06	0.31
AR (3) P-value	0.25	0.46	0.55	0.61	0.65	0.46
Hansen Test (p-value)	0.22	0.07	0.39	0.17	0.15	0.68
Difference-in-Hansen Test of Exogeneity of Instruments Subsets						
GMM instruments for level-Hansen test	0.37	0.284	0.842	0.270	0.278	0.96
Difference		0.015	0.017	0.107	0.076	0.042
gmm -Hansen test	0.47	0.392	0.901	0.492	0.292	0.98
Difference		0.016	0.031	0.047	0.107	0.07

***, ** and * denotes significant at 1%, 5% and at 10% level of significance respectively. Values in the parentheses represent the corresponding p-value. Findings are corrected for heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation problems. L1 indicates one period lagged values of corresponding variables.

The results for the whole sample and subsamples of OECD countries and developing countries under Model-1 (a) are shown in column (2), column (3) and column (4) respectively. Similarly, the estimated results of Model-1(b) for whole samples and subsamples of OECD countries and developing countries are shown in column (5), column (6) and in column (7) respectively.

The effects of lagged dependent variable remain positive and highly significant along with expected sign in both models and in the whole sample as well as in subsamples. This finding confirms the appropriateness and reliability of dynamic GMM estimators which allows the next step of verifying statistical inference of related hypotheses mentioned in section-3.1. The study found the self-reinforcing effects of the historical existence of income inequality on itself similar to the findings by Claessens and Perotti (2007). It is observed in Model-1(a), current period income inequality reduces by 0.06% due to 0.01 point (index) increases in the previous year's financial development (FD) in the whole sample. Here, the dependent variable is in logarithmic form and all independent variables are in logarithmic form except the financial development index. FD ranges from 0.05 (minimum) to 1(maximum) across samples and compares the performances and rank across countries over time. Greater value means better financial development. Now we cannot interpret its effects due to its 1-unit changes, we have to find the effects of 0.01 point(index) increase in FD on gini coefficient. Since, coefficient of lagged FD is -0.06 in the whole sample,

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta\% \text{ gini} &= (100 * \text{coefficients of } L.FD) \times \Delta L.FD \\ &\Rightarrow \Delta\% \text{ gini} = (100 * -0.06) \times 0.01 \\ &= -0.06\%, \text{ exactly the same as represented in the table.}\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, all of the coefficients of FD variables could be interpreted in percentage terms as they remain same after manual calculation.

Income inequality also reduces due to increases in the previous year's financial development in both country groups. But the results are statistically significant only at a 10 percent level of significance for the whole sample and for developing countries which becomes insignificant in case of OECD countries. Inflation is found to have no significant effect in all cases. Real GDP exaggerates the income inequality in general and this effect is highly significant in developing countries. This result supports the recent argument that the trickle-down effect of growth is not happening anymore and the situation is even worse in developing countries.

The estimated results of Model-1(b) indicate that lagged one period financial development significantly reduces income equality and the magnitude of this effect is higher in OECD countries than in developing countries. Besides, the squared financial development is found to significantly exaggerate the income inequality and the magnitude of this effect is higher in developing countries than in OECD countries. This result strongly supports the non-linear U-shaped hypothesis as the opposite of the theoretical inverse U-shaped prediction of Greenwood and Jovanovic (1990). Like, Korinek and Kreamer (2014), it is confirmed here that initially, income

inequality decreases due to an increase in financial development but after a certain level of development, income inequality increases with further development of the financial system. The effects of inflation and real GDP remain similar as explained under Model-1(a).

The accuracy of these findings is further judged by the diagnostic tests of autocorrelation and overidentifying restrictions. In the case of Model-1(a), second-order autocorrelation AR (2) is observed in all cases except in the case of OECD subsample. And in Model 1(b) it is found only in the whole sample. But the p-value of AR (3) strictly rejects the presence of third-order autocorrelation in all cases of Table-3. The presence of AR (2) weakens the estimated results. The OECD subsample of Model-1 (a), The OECD countries and developing countries subsamples of Model-1 (b) reject the presence of second-order autocorrelation which increases the strength of the findings of those models. In addition, the p-value of Hansen test is greater than 0.05 in all cases indicating the failure of rejecting the null hypothesis that overidentifying restrictions of instruments are valid. Also, the number of instruments is lower than the number of groups in case.

This study also adopted the traditional measure of financial development namely private credit as a percentage of GDP. The estimated results of both linear and non-linear effects of private credit on income inequality are shown in Appendix Table-A4. The estimated results show that the lagged dependent variable significantly increases present income inequality in all samples of both models. Also, estimated results satisfy the diagnostic tests of AR (1), AR (2) and Hansen Tests for all cases except in the whole sample of Model-2 (a) where the presence of second-order autocorrelation could not be rejected. The number of instruments is also lower than the number of groups in all samples. The lagged one period private credit is found to reduce income inequality in Model-2(b) only for developing countries but at a 10 percent level of significance. Also, the effects of squared private credit remain insignificant. It could be concluded that the use of the overall Financial Development Index is more informative and significant than using a partial measure of it. Therefore, the rest of the study is continued by using the overall financial development index.

4.2.2 Effects of Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI) on Income Inequality

Tan and Law (2012) examined only the effects of corruption. Extending their study, attempts are made here to identify the effects of other five dimensions of governance besides Corruption Control in separate equations. And to get the interactive effects of those five indicators with Corruption Control.

(i) Corruption Control

The estimated results of regression equation-3 are represented in Table-4. This model is correctly specified as the lagged dependent variable has significantly income inequality exaggerating effect and there are no second or higher-order autocorrelation problems. Also, Hansen test fails to reject the hypothesis of no overidentifying restrictions and the number of instruments is lower than the number of groups. In

this Table-4, the negative effect of one period lagged financial development and negative effects of squared lagged financial development remain highly significant in OECD countries and developing countries but not for the whole sample. The better Corruption Control reduces income inequality in the whole sample which is mainly a phenomenon of the developing country since the finding is insignificant in the case of OECD countries. But the statistical significance of the former result is very weak.

Table 4 : Effects of Corruption Control on Income inequality

(1) Variable	Model-3 : Effects of Corruption Control		
	(2) Whole Sample	(3) OECD Countries	(4) Developing Countries
L1. gini	2.34 (0.00) ***	0.82 (0.00) ***	0.91 (0.00) ***
L1. FD	-0.02 (0.83)	-0.56 (0.01) **	-0.59 (0.01) **
L1. FD ²	0.03 (0.65)	0.39 (0.02) **	0.46 (0.04) **
inflation	-0.003 (.75)	-0.02 (0.49)	0.01 9 (0.42)
rgdp	0.004 (0.34)	0.02 (0.05) *	0.02 (0.02) **
corruption_cont	-0.07 (0.05) *	-0.04 (0.31)	-0.08 (0.06) *
Constant	0.13 (0.46)	0.40 (0.53)	0.13 (0.77)
Observations no.	1204	559	581
Group no.	81	35	37
Instruments no.	20	21	21
Diagnostic Test Results			
F-Value	412.69	5.82	30.40
Prob> F	0.000	0.00	0.00
AR (1) P-value	0.001	0.06	0.148
AR (2) P-value	0.241	0.06	0.245
AR (3) P-value	0.08	0.687	0.285
Hansen Test (p value)	0.281	0.128	0.783
Difference-in-Hansen Test of Exogeneity of Instruments Subsets			
GMM instruments for level -Hansen Test	0.313	0.233	0.969
Difference	0.258	0.086	0.079
Gmm-Hansen test	0.385	0.267	0.994
Difference	0.215	0.10	0.116

***, ** and * denotes significant at 1%, 5% and at 10% level of significance respectively. Values in the parentheses represent the corresponding p-value. Findings are corrected for heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation problems. L1 indicates one period lagged values of corresponding variables.

(ii) Effects of Government Effectiveness

The estimated results of regression model-4(a) and 4(b) by using Government Effectiveness to represent governance are represented in Table-5. No significant effects of Government Effectiveness and its interaction with Corruption Control have been found across all samples and all subsamples. Government Effectiveness does not have any direct or interactive effect with Corruption Control on income inequality. While examining the validity of underlying assumptions, it is found that these models for the whole sample and subsample of OECD countries were suffering from second-order autocorrelation. To solve the AR (2) problem, the two-period lagged value of Gini index has been added in those samples. But in the case of developing countries, no AR (2) or higher-order autocorrelation is found. The specified models are valid since the lagged dependent variables have a significant effect. The AR (2) test of autocorrelation and Hansen test of over-identifying restrictions are valid. The number of instruments is also lower than the number of groups.

Table 5 : Effects of Government Effectiveness on Income inequality

(1) Variable	Model-4 (a) : Without interaction term			Model-4 (b) : With interaction term		
	(2) Whole Sample	(3) OECD Countries	(4) Developing Countries	(5) Whole Sample	(6) OECD Countries	(7) Developing Countries
L1. gini	2.30 (0.00) ***	1.39 (0.06)	0.90 (0.00) ***	2.28 (0.00) ***	1.44 (0.11)	0.91 (0.00) ***
L2. gini	-1.29 (0.00) ***	-0.45 (0.47)		-1.27 (0.00) ***	-0.51 (0.51)	
L1. FD	0.01 (0.92)	-0.34 (0.20)	-0.58 (0.01) **	-0.03 (0.65)	-0.33 (0.25)	-.58 (0.01) **
L1. FD ²	0.001 (0.99)	0.24 (0.18)	0.47 (0.02) **	0.03 (0.65)	0.23 (0.21)	0.45 (0.04) **
inflation	-0.01 (0.44)	-0.02 (0.25)	0.003 (0.64)	-0.004 (0.58)	-0.02 (0.29)	0.01 (0.50)
rgdp	-0.003 (0.54)	0.02 (0.15)	0.02 (0.03) **	0.01 (0.27)	0.02 (0.22)	0.02 (0.02) **
govt_effectiveness	0.04 (0.23)	0.01 (0.87)	- 0.06 (0.18)	0.03 (0.59)	-0.08 (0.43)	0.05 (0.61)
govt_effectiveness × corruption_cont	-	-	-	-0.01 (0.12)	-0.004 (0.79)	-0.02 (0.14)
Constant	0.99 (0.62)	0.36 (0.31)	0.21 (0.71)	-0.02 (0.94)	0.33 (0.35)	-.08 (0.87)
Observations no.	1204	524	581	1204	524	581

Groups no.	81	35	37	81	35	37
Instruments no.	20	20	21	20	20	21
Diagnostic Test Results						
Wald χ^2	3746.18	F, 19.46	129.55	F, 405.83	F, 19.71	F, 25.06
Prob> F	0.000	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
AR (1) P-value	0.001	0.359	0.213	0.001	0.420	0.158
AR (2) P-value	0.267	0.226	0.296	0.262	0.269	0.251
AR (3) P-value	0.080	0.337	0.495	0.080	0.368	0.303
Hansen Test (p value)	0.17	0.418	0.603	0.258	0.339	0.673
Difference-in-Hansen Test of Exogeneity of Instruments Subsets						
GMM instruments Level-Hansen test	0.23	0.816	0.921	0.24	0.740	0.958
Difference	0.17	0.042	0.046	0.37	0.042	0.053
Gmm -Hansen test	0.60	0.842	0.967	0.51	0.744	0.997
Difference	0.04	0.085	0.074	0.13	0.091	0.067

***, ** and * denotes significant at 1%, 5% and at 10% level of significance respectively. Values in the parentheses represent the corresponding p-value. Findings are corrected for heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation problems. L1 and L2 indicate one period and two period lagged values of corresponding variables respectively.

(iii) Effect of Regulatory Quality

The estimated results of regression Model-4(a) and 4(b) using Regulatory Quality to represent governance has been presented in Table-6. Regulatory Quality does not have any direct significant effect on income inequality. However, as seen in column (5) of Table-6, the sign of interaction term of Regulatory Quality with Corruption Control is negative which is mainly due to developing countries as shown in column (7) but this is insignificant for OECD countries as seen in column (6).

Table 6 : Effects of Regulatory Quality on Income Inequality

(1) Variable	Model-4 (a) : Without interaction term			Model-4 (b) : With interaction term		
	(2) Whole Sample	(3) OECD Countries	(4) Developing Countries	(5) Whole Sample	(6) OECD Countries	(7) Developing Countries
L1. gini	2.44 (0.00) ***	0.085 (0.00) ***	0.91 (0.00) ***	2.40 (0.00)	0.85 (0.00) ***	0.91 (0.00) ***
L2. gini	-1.41 (0.00) ***			-1.36 (0.00) ***		

L1. FD	0.05 (0.60)	-0.58 (0.03) **	-0.61 (0.02) **	0.006 (0.95)	-0.58 (0.02) **	-0.64 (0.01) **
L1. FD ²	-0.02 (0.79)	0.41 (0.03) **	0.51 (0.04) **	0.01 (0.88)	0.40 (0.02) **	0.49 (0.04) **
inflation	-0.003 (0.72)	-0.01 (0.51)	0.003 (0.75)	-0.002 (0.85)	-0.01 (0.48)	0.006 (0.59)
rgdp	0.0005 (0.91)	0.03 (0.01) **	0.02 (0.06) *	0.003 (0.40)	0.03 (0.02) **	0.03 (0.02) **
regu_quality	-0.01 (0.79)	-0.08 (0.38)	0.22 (0.77)	0.05 (0.36)	-0.05 (0.65)	0.14 (0.16)
regu_quality × corruption_cont	-	-	-	-0.02 (0.05) *	-0.01 (0.51)	-0.02 (0.05) *
Constant	-0.06 (0.75)	0.41 (0.51)	-0.20 (0.70)	-0.12 (0.55)	0.39 (0.51)	-0.44 (0.36)
Observations no.	1204	559	581	1204	559	581
Group no.	81	35	37	81	35	37
Instruments no.	20	21	21	20	21	21
Diagnostic Test Results						
F-Value	408.80	5.63	22.14	314.93	5.24	25.87
Prob> F	0.000	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
AR (1) P-value	0.002	0.064	0.209	0.001	0.058	0.169
AR (2) P-value	0.22	0.06	0.36	0.23	0.06	0.37
AR (3) P-value	0.08	0.65	0.49	0.04	0.68	0.32
Hansen Test	0.12	0.22	0.64	0.23	0.17	0.79
Difference-in-Hansen Test of Exogeneity of Instruments Subsets						
GMM instruments Level –Hansen test	0.21	0.37	0.94	0.24	0.31	0.96
Difference	0.09	0.09	0.05	0.28	0.09	0.11
gmm -Hansen test	0.62	0.54	0.97	0.52	0.45	0.99
Difference	0.02	0.06	0.08	0.09	0.06	0.15

***, ** and * denotes significant at 1%, 5% and at 10% level of significance respectively. Values in the parentheses represent the corresponding p-value. Findings are corrected for heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation problems. L1 and L2 indicate one period and two period lagged values of corresponding variables respectively.

So, it might be concluded that better Regulatory Quality combined with strong Corruption Control or strong Corruption Control combined with better Regulatory Quality could narrow down the income gap in developing countries. This is significant only at a 10 percent level of significance. The results of the validity of models are the same as the previous subsection.

(iv) Effects of Rule of Law

The estimated results of regression Model-4(a) and 4(b) using Rule of Law as a governance indicator has been presented in Table-7. Exactly similar to the previous subsection these models satisfy all underlying assumption except AR (2) in the whole sample only and to solve it the two-period lagged values of dependent variable has been added with the models where needed.

Table 7 : Effects of Rule of Law on Income Inequality

(1) Variable	Model-4 (a) : Without interaction term			Model-4 (b) : With interaction term		
	(2) Whole Sample	(3) OECD Countries	(4) Developing Countries	(5) Whole Sample	(6) OECD Countries	(7) Developing Countries
L1. Gini	2.23 (0.00) ***	0.82 (0.00) ***	0.89 (0.00) ***	2.19 (0.00) ***	0.82 (0.00) ***	0.90 (0.00) ***
L2. Gini	-1.23 (0.00) ***			-1.21 (0.00) ***		
L1. FD	-0.01 (0.89)	0.54 (0.02) **	-0.62 (0.01) **	-0.05 (0.58)	-0.53 (0.02) **	-0.61 (0.01) **
L1. FD ²	0.01 (0.86)	0.37 (0.03) **	0.51 (0.02) **	0.04 (0.52)	0.36 (0.03) **	0.47 (0.03) **
Inflation	-0.006 (0.45)	-0.03 (0.15)	0.001 (0.81)	-0.005 (0.57)	-0.03 (0.16)	0.01 (0.59)
Rgdp	0.003 (0.45)	0.03 (0.01) **	0.02 (0.02) **	0.006 (0.21)	0.03 (0.01) **	0.03 (0.01) **
rule_law	-0.04 (0.24)	-0.09 (0.13)	-0.07 (0.13)	0.04 (0.48)	-0.06 (0.43)	0.02 (0.76)
rule_law × corruption_cont				-0.02 (0.07) *	-0.01 (0.49)	-0.02 (0.10)
Constant	0.12 (0.57)	0.52 (0.33)	0.21 (0.73)	0.02 (0.93)	0.54 (0.31)	0.02 (0.97)
Observations no.	1204	559	581	1204	559	581
Group no.	81	35	37	81	35	37
Instruments no.	20	21	21	20	21	21

Diagnostic Test Results						
F-Value	552.69	7.21	21.91	456.62	6.55	24.36
Prob> F	0.000	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
AR (1) P-value	0.002	0.06	0.23	0.001	0.05	0.18
AR (2) P-value	0.29	0.05	0.35	0.29	0.06	0.29
AR (3) P-value	0.08	0.64	0.45	0.09	0.66	0.32
Hansen Test (p value)	0.16	0.27	0.62	0.26	0.22	0.68
Difference-in-Hansen Test of Exogeneity of Instruments Subsets						
GMM instruments for level – Hansen test	0.21	0.37	0.93	0.23	0.30	0.95
Difference	0.17	0.16	0.05	0.43	0.16	0.06
gmm-Hansen test	0.50	0.39	0.97	0.42	0.34	0.99
Difference	0.05	0.19	0.08	0.17	0.16	0.11

***, ** and * denotes significant at 1%, 5% and at 10% level of significance respectively. Values in the parentheses represent corresponding p-value. Findings are corrected for heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation problems. L1 and L2 indicates one period and two period lagged values of corresponding variables respectively.

In all models, the direct effect of the Rule of Law on income inequality is found as insignificant.

However, as seen in column (5) the sign of interaction term of Rule of Law with Corruption Control is negative and significant at a 10 percent level of significance. It means the Rule of Law could reduce income inequality while combined with Corruption Control in the whole sample but not in subsamples.

(v) Effects of Political Stability & Absence of Violence

Using Political Stability & Absence of Violence in place of governance of regression model-4(a) and 4(b) has been estimated and results are presented in Table-8.

Table 8 : Effects of Political Stability & Absence of Violence on Income Inequality

(1) Variable	Model-4 (a) : Without interaction term			Model-4 (b) : With interaction term		
	(2) Whole Sample	(3) OECD Countries	(4) Developing Countries	(5) Whole Sample	(6) OECD Countries	(7) Developing Countries
L1. gini	2.48 (0.00) ***	0.82 (0.00) ***	0.92 (0.00) ***	2.42 (0.00) ****	0.82 (0.00) ***	0.92 (0.00) ***
L2. gini	-1.48 (0.00) ***			-1.42 (0.00) ***		

L1. FD	0.06 (0.48)	-0.57 (0.03) **	-0.55 (0.02) **	0.01 (0.89)	-0.55 (0.02) **	-0.57 (0.02) **
L1. FD ²	-0.04 (0.53)	0.39 (0.03) **	0.45 (0.05) *	-0.01 (0.90)	0.38 (0.03) **	0.43 (0.06) *
inflation	0.002 (0.79)	-0.01 (0.69)	0.005 (0.58)	0.003 (0.69)	-0.01 (0.70)	0.01 (0.42)
rgdp	-0.01 (0.80)	0.03 (0.03) **	0.02 (0.07) *	0.002 (0.61)	0.02 (0.05) *	0.02 (0.03) **
political_stability & av	-0.02 (0.02) **	-0.02 (0.31)	0.01 (0.72)	0.04 (0.23)	0.02 (0.65)	0.08 (0.06) *
political_stability & av × corruption_cont				-0.02 (0.07) *	-0.01 (0.29)	-0.02 (0.08) *
Constant	0.08 (0.63)	0.24 (0.69)	-0.12 (0.78)	0.02 (0.92)	0.29 (0.62)	-0.21 (0.59)
Observations no.	1204	559	581	1204	559	581
Groups no.	81	35	37	81	35	37
Instruments no.	20	21	21	20	21	21
Diagnostic Test Results						
F-Value	478.86	5.80	19.93	436.89	5.46	25.27
Prob> F	0.000	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
AR (1) P-value	0.001	0.06	0.196	0.001	0.060	0.14
AR (2) P-value	0.27	0.06	0.25	0.28	0.07	0.21
AR (3) P-value	0.07	0.60	0.47	0.07	0.65	0.28
Hansen Test (p-value)	0.47	0.14	0.61	0.63	0.11	0.73
Difference-in-Hansen Test of Exogeneity of Instruments Subsets						
GMM instruments for level- Hansen test	0.60	0.23	0.95	0.61	0.18	0.96
Difference	0.18	0.11	0.04	0.45	0.11	0.08
gmm-Hansen test	0.74	0.26	0.99	0.69	0.22	0.11
Difference	0.16	0.13	0.05	0.37	0.11	0.11

***, ** and * denotes significant at 1%, 5% and at 10% level of significance respectively. The corresponding p-value is represented in the parentheses. Findings are corrected for heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation problems. L1 and L2 indicate one period and two period lagged of corresponding variables respectively.

Since the whole sample models were suffering from AR (2) problem, the two-period lagged of gini is included in whole sample only. These models satisfy all other diagnostic tests including AR (2), Hansen tests and less instrument numbers. The index of Political Stability & Absence of Violence/Terrorism measures perceptions of the likelihood that the government will be destabilized or overthrown by unconstitutional or violent means, including politically-motivated violence and terrorism.

For the whole sample, strong Political Stability is found to reduce income inequality directly with a high level of significance as shown in column (2) but the result becomes insignificant while examining in developing countries and OECD countries. When the interactive term of Political Stability and Corruption Control is added, its single effect becomes insignificant except in OECD countries. In OECD countries, an adverse effect of Political Stability has been found which could be significantly (at a 10 % level of significance) mitigated while Political Stability combined with Corruption Control. This result is true in the whole sample as well as in OECD countries but not in developing countries.

(vi) Effects of Voice & Accountability

The estimated results of regression model-4(a) and 4(b) representing governance with Voice & Accountability has been presented in Table-9.

Table 9 : Effects of Voice & Accountability

(1) Variable	Model-4 (a) : Without interaction term			Model-4 (b) : With interaction term		
	(2) Whole Sample	(3) OECD Countries	(4) Developing Countries	(5) Whole Sample	(6) OECD Countries	(7) Developing Countries
L1. gini	0.78 (0.00) ***	0.81 (0.00) ***	0.93 (0.00) ***	0.78 (0.00) ***	0.80 (0.00) ***	0.93 (0.00) ***
L1. FD	-0.61 (0.00) ***	-0.67 (0.02) **	-0.65 (0.01) **	-0.60 (0.00) ***	-0.64 (0.01) **	-0.64 (0.01) **
L1. FD ²	0.44 (0.00) ***	0.45 (0.02) **	0.54 (0.02) **	0.41 (0.00) ***	0.43 (0.01) **	0.49 (0.04) **
inflation	-0.003 (0.55)	-0.01 (0.53)	0.002 (0.81)	0.001 (0.92)	-0.01 (0.53)	0.01 (0.58)
rgdp	0.03 (0.00) ****	0.02 (0.03) **	0.02 (0.05) *	0.03 (0.00) ***	0.02 (0.05) *	0.03 (0.02) **
voice_accountancy	-0.07 (0.27)	-0.11 (0.30)	-0.08 (0.43)	-0.06 (0.37)	-0.08 (0.43)	0.01 (0.94)

voice_accountancy × corruption_cont				-0.01 (0.08) *	-0.01 (0.29)	-0.02 (0.11)
Constant	0.60 (0.26)	0.73 (0.36)	0.11 (0.87)	0.71 (0.15)	0.86 (0.28)	-0.003 (1.11)
Observations no.	1284	559	581	1284	559	581
Groups no.	81	35	37	81	35	37
Instruments no.	21	21	21	21	21	21
Diagnostic Test Results						
F-Value	24.7	7.00	22.40	21.36	7.36	22.36
Prob> F	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
AR (1) P-value	0.01	0.05	0.22	0.01	0.04	0.19
AR (2) P-value	0.06	0.07	0.48	0.07	0.08	0.39
AR (3) P-value	0.64	0.70	0.41	0.69	0.77	0.31
Hansen Test (p value)	0.14	0.12	0.84	0.18	0.12	0.91
Difference -in-Hansen Test of Exogeneity of Instruments Subsets						
GMM instruments for level-Hansen test	0.33	0.26	0.98	0.31	0.21	0.99
Difference	0.05	0.06	0.11	0.10	0.10	0.16
Gmm-Hansen test	0.62	0.25	0.99	0.62	0.22	0.11
Difference	0.02	0.11	0.1	0.04	0.12	0.26

***, ** and * denotes significant at 1%, 5% and at 10% level of significance respectively. Values in the parentheses represent corresponding p-value. Findings are corrected for heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation problems. L1 indicates one period lagged values of corresponding variables.

Unlike the previous subsections, there is no AR (2) problem in any model. In all cases, no second or higher-order autocorrelation problem is found. As well as the effects of lagged dependent variables are found significant with the expected sign and Hansen tests confirm the validity of no overidentifying restriction. Instruments numbers are lower than the number of groups. Voice & Accountability does not have any direct significant effect on income inequality. However, as seen in column (5) the sign of interaction term of this variable with Corruption Control has become significantly negative only at a 10 percent level of significance. So, in general Voice & Accountability alone cannot influence income inequality but it could reduce income inequality while combined with Corruption Control. However, no such evidence could be obtained while examining the OECD countries and developing countries separately.

5. CONCLUSION

Since theory and empirical studies on finance-income inequality revealed conflicting results, this study re-examined the effects of financial development and governance on income inequality by using a broader concept of financial development, a more comparable Gini Index and the worldwide Governance Indicators. This study confirms the non-linear U-shaped hypothesis of finance-income inequality nexus. That is, an increase in financial development reduces income inequality initially; but at a higher level of financial development, further increase of it increases income inequality. Corruption Control reduces income inequality in general which is mainly driven by developing countries. Similarly, the interactive effects of Regulatory Quality and Corruption Control could reduce income inequality although Regulatory Quality fails to directly influence income inequality in developing countries. The influence of Rule of Law remains insignificant across all models in all groups but its interactive effects with Corruption Control contribute to reducing income inequality only in the whole sample. Political Stability is found to improve income distribution in the whole sample only. But interacting with Corruption Control, it could reduce income inequality in the whole sample which is mainly driven by developing countries where its single or direct effect is found to increase income inequality. Finally, no direct effect of Voice & Accountability is identified neither in the whole sample nor in subsamples. But while interacted with Corruption Control, it could reduce income inequality in the whole sample only. A similar result could not be found in subsample analysis. Hence, with a further high level of financial development income inequality could be worsening. Government policies designed to handle these adverse situations could be effective under strong corruption control. Therefore, there should be a hand in hand improvement of Regulatory Quality, Rule of Law, Political Stability, Voice & Accountability and Corruption Control, since under extensive corruption level, improving in other dimensions of governance would not be beneficial for the poorest quintile.

As limitations, it should be mentioned that these findings are subject to the specific sample and variables used in the study. And the sample period consists of data from 1998 to 2014 since data on income inequality for all countries were not found beyond 2014. In some cases, the significance level remains at 10%. Therefore, further research could be conducted by taking a longer time period, using alternative measures of concerning variables and improving the significance level for all variables.

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APPENDICES

Table-A1: List of Countries

Country Name					Country Group
Australia	Estonia	Ireland	Luxembourg	Slovakia Republic	OECD Countries
Austria	Finland	Israel	Mexico	Slovenia	
Belgium	France	Italy	Netherlands	Spain	
Canada	Germany	Japan	New Zealand	Sweden	
Chile	Greece	Korea	Norway	Switzerland	
Czech Republic	Hungary	Latvia	Poland	United Kingdom	
Denmark	Iceland	Lithuania	Portugal	United States	
Algeria	Co'te d'Ivoire	India	Nicaragua	Tunisia	
Bangladesh	Dominican Republic	Indonesia	Pakistan	Turkey	
Bolivia	Ecuador	Iran	Paraguay	Venezuela	
Botswana	Egypt	Jamaica	Peru	Vietnam	
Brazil	El Salvador	Jordan	Philippines	Zambia	
China	Ghana	Kenya	South Africa		
Colombia	Guatemala	Malaysia	Sri Lanka		
Costa Rica	Honduras	Morocco	Thailand		

Albania	Azerbaijan	Kazakhstan	Russia	Ukraine	Transitional Countries
Armenia	Belarus	Moldova	Serbia		

Table-A2 : Components of Financial Development Index and their Data Sources

Category	Indicators	Data Sources
Financial Institutions		
Depth	Private sector credit to GDP	FinStats 2015
	Pension fund to GDP	
	Mutual fund assets to GDP	
	Insurance premiums, life and non-life to GDP	
Access	Bank branches per 100,000 adults	FinStats 2015 IMF Financial Access Survey
	ATMs per 100,000 adults	
Efficiency	Net interest margin	FinStats 2015
	Lending-deposits spread	
	Non-interest income to total income	
	Overhead costs to total assets	
	Return on assets	
	Return on equity	
Financial Markets		
Depth	Stock Market Capitalization to GDP	FinStats 2015 FinStats 2015 BIS debt securities database Dealogic corporate debt database Dealogic corporate debt database
	Stocks traded to GDP	
	International debt securities to government to GDP	
	Total debt securities of financial corporations to GDP	
	Total debt securities of nonfinancial corporations to GDP	
Access	Percent of market capitalization outside of top 10 largest companies	FinStats 2015
	Total number of issuers of debt (domestic and external, nonfinancial and financial corporations)	
Efficiency	Stock market turnover ratio (stock traded to capitalization)	FinStats 2015

Source: IMF Working Paper by Svirydzhenka (2016)

Table-A3 : Definition of Variables and Data Sources

Variable Name	Definition	Data Sources
Gini Index	Gini coefficient is the disposable (post tax, post transfer) Gini Index.	Standardized World Income Inequality Database (SWIID) 2016 (Version 6.2) by Solt (2016)
FD Index	Overall Financial Development in terms of Market and Institutional access, depth and efficiency	Financial Development Database (2016) by IMF.
Private Credit	Private credit by deposit money banks and other financial institutions to GDP (%)	World Bank's Global Financial Development Database, 2017
Real GDP	GDP (constant 2010 US\$)	World Bank and OECD National Accounts data files.
Inflation	Measured by Consumer Price Index (CPI)	International Financial Statistics and data files, IMF

WGI	Worldwide Governance Indicators	World Bank Development Research Group
(i) Corruption Control	Control of Corruption captures perceptions of the extent to which public power is exercised for private gain, including both petty and grand forms of corruption, as well as "capture" of the state by elites and private interests.	
(ii) Government Effectiveness	Government Effectiveness captures perceptions of the quality of public services, the quality of the civil service and the degree of its independence from political pressures, the quality of policy formulation and implementation, and the credibility of the government's commitment to such policies.	
(iii) Regulatory Quality	Regulatory Quality captures perceptions of the ability of the government to formulate and implement sound policies and regulations that permit and promote private sector development.	
(iv) Rule of Law	Rule of Law captures perceptions of the extent to which agents have confidence in and abide by the rules of society, and in particular the quality of contract enforcement, property rights, the police, and the courts, as well as the likelihood of crime and violence.	
(v) Political Stability and Absence of violence	Political Stability and Absence of Violence/Terrorism measures perceptions of the likelihood of political instability and/or politically-motivated violence, including terrorism.	
(vi) Voice and Accountability	Voice and Accountability capture perceptions of the extent to which a country's citizens can participate in selecting their government, as well as freedom of expression, freedom of association, and free media.	

Note: Percentile rank indicates the country's rank among all countries covered by the aggregate indicator, with 0 corresponding to lowest rank, and 100 to highest rank. The greater value indicates a better outcome.

Table-A4 : Private Credit and Income inequality

(1) Variable	Model-2(a) : Linear			Model-2(b) : Non-Linear		
	(2) Whole Sample	(2) OECD Countries	(3) Developing Countries	(4) Whole Sample	(5) OECD Countries	(6) Developing Countries
L1. gini	0.085 (0.00) ***	0.87 (0.00) ***	0.61 (0.03) **	0.85 (0.00) ***	0.91 (0.00) ***	0.73 (0.00) ***
L1. Private_Credit	0.0003 (0.06) *	9.12 (0.11)	-0.0004 (0.52)	-0.002 (0.21)	2.10e-06 (0.11)	-0.002 (0.08) *
L1. Private_Credit ²				5.74e-06 (1.33)	7.89e-08 (0.98)	0.00001 (0.11)
inflation	0.01 (0.37)	-0.004 (0.84)	0.01 (0.32)	-0.002 (0.81)	-0.0035 (0.92)	-0.002 (0.71)
rgdp	- 0.01 (0.12)	-0.004 (0.86)	-0.01 (0.574)	0.0001 (0.99)	0.0007 (0.97)	-0.002 (0.94)
Constant	0.73 (0.80)	0.51 (0.42)	1.64 (0.13)	0.58 (0.25)	0.31 (0.72)	1.14 (0.38)
Observation no.	1284	559	581	1284	559	581
Group no.	81	35	37	81	35	37
Instruments no.	21	21	21	21	21	21
Diagnostic Test Results						
F-Value	14.26	21.87	5.72	15.64	18.88	16.45
Prob> F	0.000	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
AR (1) P-value	0.03	0.03	0.88	0.64	0.18	0.99
AR (2) P-value	0.03	0.15	0.69	0.08	0.25	0.66
AR (3) P-value	0.21	0.45	0.22	0.77	0.46	0.31
Hansen Test (p value)	0.01	0.10	0.67	0.12	0.09	0.87
Difference-in-Hansen Test of Exogeneity of Instruments subsets						
GMM instruments Level -Hansen test	0.091	0.432	0.89	0.44	0.31	0.98
Difference	0.003	0.010	0.08	0.01	0.02	0.11
gmm -Hansen test	0.48	0.31	0.83	0.78	0.24	0.96
Difference	0.000	0.051	0.23	0.01	0.07	0.29

***, ** and * denotes significant at 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance respectively. Values in the parentheses represent corresponding p-value. Findings are corrected for heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation problems. L1 indicates one period lagged values of the corresponding variables.